

4(3'-Coumarinyl)-2-Arylamino Thiazoles and Some of Their Derivatives

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Nine 4-(3'-coumarinyl) 2-arylamino thiazoles, their 5-bromo and acetoxy-mercuri derivatives have been synthesised for possible use as fungicides.

In course of our studies on thiazole compounds¹⁻¹³ it appeared to us of considerable interest to prepare some 4(3'-coumarinyl) 2-arylamino thiazoles and their 5-bromo and acetoxy-mercuri derivatives as potential fungicides.

4-(3'-coumarinyl) 2-arylamino thiazoles have been prepared by condensing 3-(ω -bromoacetyl)coumarin with corresponding arylthioureas in alcohol¹⁵.

In view of the fact that halogens confer fungicidal activity on a compound and introduction of halogen, particularly bromine, into the thiazole nucleus is expected to increase the bactericidal and fungicidal properties of the thiazole compounds considerably¹²⁻¹⁴, bromination of these thiazoles have been undertaken in the hope that it may lead to production of more potent fungicides.

It is known that pronounced antibacterial and fungicidal activities are also associated with mercurated thiazoles⁵⁻¹⁰, benzothiazoles¹⁶, thiazolidones¹⁷⁻²⁰ and thiazolines²¹. So it was of interest to prepare some new mercuri derivatives of thiazoles and 5-bromothiazoles.

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The thiazoles have been mercurated using mercuric acetate to give acetoxy mercury compounds in which the acetoxy-mercuri group enters the aryl nucleus attached to -NH group. This assumption is justified because it has been found that 4-(3'-coumarinyl)2-acetylamino thiazole does not undergo mercuration under the experimental conditions adopted in the present investigation for the mercuration of 4-(3'-coumarinyl) 2-arylamino thiazoles. This clearly shows that acetoxy-mercuri group does not enter the coumarin nucleus attached directly to the thiazole group at the fourth carbon atom. On the basis of earlier observations on the mercuration of aromatic amines and phenols²²⁻²³ and 5-arylidene-2- α -naphthylimino-4-thiazolidones, it has been assumed that the acetoxy-mercuri group enters the *para* position (with respect to NH group) of the aryl nucleus in the thiazole base and if the *para* position is blocked, substitution occurs at the *ortho* position.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-(3'-coumarinyl) 2-amino-phenyl thiazole: To a solution of 3-(ω -bromoacetyl)-coumarin (0.01M) in 20 ml of alcohol, phenyl thiourea (0.01M) was added and the mixture heated to give a clear solution. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 2 hrs. on a water-bath. Crystals of 4-(3'-coumarinyl) 2-aminophenyl thiazole were separated, filtered and finally crystallised from alcohol as yellow needles. (m.p. 248°, yield 65%) (Found: C-67.18%, H-3.54%, S-9.86%, N-8.66%, C₁₈H₁₂O₂N₂S requires C-67.51%, H-3.75%, S-10.0%, N-8.75%).

The melting point and the analytical data of the 4-(3'-coumarinyl) 2-aminoaryl thiazoles are given in Table-I.

TABLE I

4-(3'-coumarinyl) 2-amino aryl thiazoles

Compound No.	Nature of aryl group R	M P. °C	Yield %	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	phenyl	248	65	8.66	8.75	9.86	10.00
2.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	229	70	7.85	7.97	8.78	9.02
3.	<i>p</i> -bromophenyl	237	75	6.96	7.02	7.90	8.02
4.	<i>p</i> -nitrophenyl	262	65	11.42	11.50	8.59	8.76
5.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	233	70	8.15	8.38	9.42	9.58
6.	<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	235	60	7.86	8.00	8.96	9.14
7.	<i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl	160	65	7.41	7.56	8.69	8.79
8.	α -naphthyl	170	55	7.58	7.69	8.58	8.64
9.	β -naphthyl	201	60	7.59	7.69	8.51	8.64

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5-Bromo-4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-aminophenyl thiazole : 4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-aminophenyl thiazole (3.2 g) was treated with hydrobromic acid (conc. 3 ml.) and the hydrobromide salt was dissolved in 25 ml of glacial acetic acid. The mixture was stirred and well cooled under ice. Bromine (3 g.) dissolved in acetic acid (25 ml) was added dropwise to the above. The whole mixture was then stirred for another hour. The excess acetic acid was distilled under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with water and basified with concentrated ammonium hydroxide. The free aminobase liberated was crystallised from alcohol as yellow needles. (m.p. 160°, yield 65%) (Found : C-53.98%, H-2.54%, N-6.96%, S-7.91%, Br-19.89%, $C_{18}H_{11}O_2N_2SBr$ requires C-54.16%, H-2.75%, N-7.02%, S-8.02%, Br-20.04%).

The melting point and analytical data of 5-bromo-4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-aminophenyl thiazoles are given in Table II.

TABLE II

5-Bromo-4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-aminophenyl thiazoles

Comp- ound No.	Nature of aryl group R	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Bromine		% Sulphur	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	phenyl	160	65	19.89	20.04	7.91	8.02
2.	<i>p</i> -chloro phenyl	109	70	18.31	18.45	7.31	7.38
3.	<i>p</i> -bromo phenyl	185	75	33.31	33.47	6.62	6.69
4.	<i>p</i> -nitro phenyl	132	65	17.72	17.81	7.14	7.20
5.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	125	70	19.12	19.36	7.61	7.75
6.	<i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl	130	65	18.54	18.64	7.41	7.46
7.	<i>p</i> -ethoxy phenyl	154	60	18.01	18.05	7.13	7.22
8.	α -naphthyl	137	55	17.73	17.80	6.91	7.12
9.	β -naphthyl	153	50	17.69	17.80	6.84	7.12

4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-(acetoxymercuri-phenyl amino)-thiazole : 4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-aminophenyl thiazole (3.2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol dilute acetic acid solution and to it was added an aqueous solution of mercuric acetate (1.72 g.) acidified with dilute acetic acid. Precipitation occurred after some time. The reaction mixture was kept over night. The precipitate was filtered and purified by repeated washing with hot water and finally alcohol and very dilute acetic acid. (m.p. 264°, yield 50%) (Found C-41.36%, H-2.13%, N-4.56%, S-5.29%, Hg.-34.57%, $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_2S$ Hg requires C-41.48%, H-2.41%, N-4.84%, S-5.53%, Hg-34.66%).

The melting point and analytical data of other compounds are given in Table-III.

5-Bromo-4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-(acetoxymercuri-phenylamino)thiazole : 5-Bromo-4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-phenylamino thiazole (3.9 g.) was dissolved in alcohol-dilute acetic acid solution and to it was added an aqueous solution of mercuric acetate (1.72 g.) acidified with dilute acetic acid. Precipitation started after some time. The reaction mixture was kept

overnight. The precipitate was filtered and purified by repeated washing with hot water and finally alcohol and very dilute acetic acid.

(M.p. 293°, yield 50%) (Found C-36.44%, H-1.89%, N-4.13%, S-4.82%, Br-11.99%, Hg-30.42%, C₂₀H₁₃O₄N₂S Br Hg requires C-36.51%, H-1.97%, N-4.25%, S-4.86% Br-12.15%, Hg-30.51%).

TABLE III

4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-(acetoxymercuri-arylamino) thiazoles

Compound No.	Nature of aryl group R	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Mercury		% Sulphur	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	phenyl	264	50	34.57	34.66	5.29	5.53
2.	<i>p</i> -chloro phenyl	249	55	32.66	32.72	5.13	5.21
3.	<i>p</i> -bromo phenyl	270	55	30.41	30.51	4.71	4.86
4.	<i>p</i> -nitro phenyl	293	50	31.92	32.17	5.03	5.13
5.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	267	45	33.53	33.86	5.29	5.40
6.	<i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl	282	55	32.72	32.96	5.20	5.25
7.	<i>p</i> -ethoxy phenyl	242	55	32.13	32.22	5.08	5.14
8.	α -naphthyl	223	58	31.85	31.91	5.11	5.09
9.	β -naphthyl	237	50	31.75	31.91	5.15	5.09

The melting point and the analytical data of other compounds are given in Table-IV.

TABLE IV

5-Bromo-4-(3'-coumarinyl)-2-(acetoxymercuri-arylamino) thiazoles

Compound No.	Nature of aryl group R	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Mercury		% Sulphur	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	phenyl	293	50	30.42	30.51	4.78	4.86
2.	<i>p</i> -chloro phenyl	271	55	28.69	28.98	4.51	4.62
3.	<i>p</i> -bromo phenyl	289	60	27.13	22.24	4.32	4.34
4.	<i>p</i> -nitro phenyl	235	50	28.32	28.55	4.49	4.55
5.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	261	55	29.69	29.87	4.71	4.76
6.	<i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl	278	57	28.99	29.17	4.58	4.65
7.	<i>p</i> -ethoxy phenyl	265	52	28.31	28.60	4.40	4.56
8.	α -naphthyl	240	54	28.12	28.35	4.55	4.52
9.	β -naphthyl	254	50	28.19	28.35	4.43	4.52

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